

‘You’ll be an archer my son!’ The ubiquity of the Cretan archer in ancient warfare

When a contingent of archers is mentioned in the context of Greek and Roman armies, more often than not the culture associated with them is that of Crete. Indeed, when we just have archers mentioned in an army without a specified origin, Cretan archers are commonly assumed to be meant, so ubiquitous with archery and groups of mercenary archers were the Cretans. The Cretans are the most famous, but certainly not the only ‘nation’ associated with a particular fighting style (Rhodian slingers and Thracian peltasts leap to mind but there are others too). The long history of Cretan archers can be seen in the sources – according to some stretching from the First Messenian War right down to the fall of Constantinople in 1453. Even in the reliable historical record we find Cretan archer units from the Peloponnesian War well into the Roman period.

Associations with the Bow

Crete had had a long association with archery. Several Linear B tablets from Knossos refer to arrow-counts (6,010 on one and 2,630 on another) as well as archers being depicted on seals and mosaics. Diodorus Siculus (5.74.5) recounts the story of Apollo that:

‘as the discoverer of the bow he taught the people of the land all about the use of the bow, this being the reason why the art of archery is especially cultivated by the Cretans and the bow is called “Cretan.” ’

The first reliable references to Cretan archers as a unit, however, which fit with our ideas about developments in ancient warfare, seem to come in the context of the Peloponnesian War (431-404 BCE). There are earlier references but these hardly seem credible. Ctesias of Cnidus (as summarised by Photius *Bibliotheca* 39b) mentions Cretan archers at the battle of Salamis in 480. This explicitly contradicts Herodotus (7.171) who tells us that the Cretans did not send support. Archers are mentioned at Psyttaleia by Aeschylus (*Persae* 460-2), and Plato (*Laws* 707b) has Clinias of Crete say that the Cretans affirm that Salamis saved Greece which might suggest a belief that they were involved. There were also archers at Plataea (Herodotus 9.22 and 9.60) although where they came from is not mentioned. Cretans are a possibility if we reject Herodotus’ statement that they did not contribute to the cause. It is, of course, dangerous to assume that when archers are mentioned, and with no more to go on, that they must have been Cretans although, as we shall see, this assumption is one our sources commonly share. It also seems unlikely that the use of mercenary troops like Cretan archer contingents were popular before the last third of the fifth

century BCE during the Peloponnesian War. It is, however, not so easy to dismiss an early date for the Cretan archer.

History or Myth?

Plutarch's life of Lycurgus provides a record of the Cretan *Agoge* which refers to the military education of Cretan youth and the messing of the men together; something Lycurgus would copy from Crete and later model at Sparta (*Lycurgus* 4). Of course, the problems with the semi-mythical Lycurgus, whose dates range from the 12th century BCE down to the 7th, mean that there is very little solid we can make of this Cretan *Agoge*. It would seem to predate the Spartan system whenever it occurred. According to Strabo (10.4.16) this Cretan system of messes (or *Andreia*) were to promote courage and not cowardice and that:

‘from boyhood they should grow up accustomed to arms and toils, so as to scorn heat, cold, marches over rugged and steep roads, and blows received in gymnasiums or regular battles; and that they should practise, not only archery, but also the war-dance ...’

It is clear from Strabo, therefore, that this Cretan constitution was tied to the idea of training Cretan youths as archers. Likewise, in Plato's *Laws*, set on Crete with a discussion about the laws needed for a Cretan colony (702C), the association of Crete with archery is made early in the dialogue (625D):

‘Under these circumstances [the rugged terrain of Crete] we are obliged to have light armour for running and to avoid any heavy equipment; so bows and arrows were adopted as suitable because of their lightness.’

The conversation in *Laws* mentions archery as part of the education of youth (794C), although the dialogue is usually taken to have a wider context than just a Cretan one. There is also evidence in the references to the Pyrrhic war dance that they may have also trained in other combat techniques but that these too were tied to archery. Plato (*Laws* 794C) also suggests training in riding, javelin and slinging. Later in the dialogue, Plato's Athenian stranger says that gymnasia should be built for riding and archery (804C) and that all youth should be trained in warfare and music. Polybius discussed the study of music at Crete for its military applications (4.20.6-12). Later still in Plato's *Laws* (834A-D), competitions ‘for peltasts’ in archery, shields, javelins and slinging are prescribed and, although horses are considered unnecessary in country as rugged as Crete's, ‘for a Cretan there is credit in being a mounted archer or javelin-man’. There seems to be enough in Plato from

the middle of the 4th century and Strabo (writing in the 1st century CE but probably using Ephorus who wrote shortly after Plato) that the Cretans were, by then at least, equated with archery. Indeed, Plato's *Laws* may have begun an interest in Crete in the 4th century BCE, an interest sparked perhaps in part by the ubiquity of its archers in armies of the time.¹ There are other sources on this institution in Crete making it more credible. Athenaeus (*Deipnosophistae* 4.143a-f) has excerpts concerning it from both the *Cretan History* of Dosiadas and the *Cretan Customs* of Pyrgion. Strabo (10.4.17) also adds that when the Cretan cities were devastated, 'they neglected military affairs' but some of the institutions 'continued in use among the Lycians, Gortynians and certain smaller cities'. Lyctus (or Lyttus) and Gortyna are certainly named among as sources for groups of mercenary archers (see Polybius 4.54-55, 5.79.10 and Pausanias 4.19.4-6). Polybius even states at 4.54.6, on the occasion of the destruction of the city in 220 BCE, that Lyttus was Crete's 'most ancient city' and the 'breeding-place of her bravest men.'

Pausanias (4.8.3, 4.10.1 and 4.19.4-6) mentions Cretan archers during both the First and Second Messenian War (in the mid-8th and early 7th century BCE). Pausanias' source for his book on Messenia was actually the Cretan poet Rhianus of Bene and the otherwise unknown Myron of Priene (4.5.1). Rhianus wrote in the 3rd century BCE (when Cretan archers were involved in virtually every battle) so that may cast doubt on his versions of events, especially having groups of Cretan mercenary archers involved in warfare so early. Pausanias is the only source for an unnamed battle during the First Messenian War where (4.8.3) 'against the Messenian light-armed troops [the Lacedaemonians] employed Cretan archers as mercenaries.' Then at 4.8.12 it is explicitly stated that the archers did not engage. Five years later (4.10.1) when the Lacedaemonians marched against Ithome the account in Pausanias goes to the trouble of stating that 'the Cretans were no longer with them.' There is one further part of Pausanias account (4.19.4-6) which features Cretan archers who had been 'summoned as mercenaries from Lyctus and other cities' and were patrolling Messenia. The passage involves the archers capturing Aristomenus and then being outwitted by a farm girl who freed Aristomenus. Doubt has been cast on these accounts and it is possible they have been influenced by a later period when mercenary groups of Cretan archers were easily hired.

'Cretans' and 'archers'

One thing to note in regard to Cretans when they are mentioned in our sources. They are always referred to as Cretan archers or just 'Cretans' (such as Plutarch *Cleomenes* 6.3 – but later at 21.3 they are named simply as archers). They are not usually associated with any other type of arms (although

¹ Glen R. Morrow *Plato's Cretan City: An Historical Interpretation of the Laws* (Princeton, 1960), pp. 24-25.

Plutarch has Pyrrhus' horse wounded by a Cretan javelin (*Pyrrhus* 29.4)). Thus, we don't find Cretan hoplites mentioned or any other kind of Cretan troops, reinforcing their identity as archers *par excellence*. There must have been other types of troops on Crete. When we read of Cretan power struggles (Polybius 4.53.3-55.6 for instance), we cannot imagine that these encounters were simply between groups of archers. There too, however, Polybius seems to be operating on the assumption that some mercenary archer contingents are implied. At 4.55.5-6 we find:

‘the Polyrrhenians and their allies sent to Philip and the Achaeans five hundred Cretans, while the Cnossians had a little earlier sent a thousand to the Aetolians and both these Cretan forces continued to take part in the present war.’

A suggestion based on Plato is that there were Cretan peltasts and slingers too and, perhaps a very small number of cavalry. In the realm of mercenary troops used in the armies of mainland Greek, Macedonian, Sicilian and Roman forces, however, they are only archers. Therefore, if ‘Cretans’ are mentioned it should be understood that they were archers. This situation of ‘archers’ being equated with Cretans is more complicated but it too has validity. Another temptation is that when a Cretan is named in foreign military service without anything further to go on, he should be considered to be connected with an archer contingent, usually as its commander. Examples of this will be examined below. Polybius (4.8.11) summarises the ‘Cretans’:

‘both by land and sea are irresistible in ambushes, forays, tricks played on the enemy, night attacks, and all petty operations which require fraud, but they are cowardly and down-hearted in the massed face-to-face charge of open battle.’

This summary suits their deployment as archers and their use as such in addition to their use in ambushes and other activities which are borne out in the sources. Even when such activities are mentioned, however, the primary function assumed for these troops is that of archer.

The Reliable Record

We now come to the ‘historical’ period of the Cretan archer, when their existence as groups of mercenaries for hire is not doubted and their presence in armies fits with our ideas about developments in warfare. Indeed, they are attested in armies all over the ancient world and from the late 5th century BCE onwards. Thucydides (2.9.4) tells us that the Cretans were on the Athenian side providing infantry and money. Even though Thucydides does not mention them as archers here, that is what is assumed they provided. Indeed, by the time of the Sicilian expedition the forces gathered included ‘archers from Athens and from Crete’ (6.25.2). At 6.43 Thucydides tells

us that this contingent was 80 strong from a total of 480 archers. There he also mentions 700 slingers, and indeed they are from Rhodes, another culture associated almost exclusively with a particular martial skill. Despite telling us that Crete was part of the Athenian alliance at 2.9.4, Thucydides states that the Cretans in Sicily were mercenaries (7.57.9-10) who ended up fighting ‘voluntarily and for pay’ against the colony of Gela which they had helped establish. Thucydides therefore gives us solid evidence of groups of Cretan archers as mercenaries. Despite the obvious desire for and appeal of mercenary work during a time of war, it is entirely possible that this practice had begun earlier on Crete.

Xenophon mentions the Cretan archers in the service of Cyrus early in the *Anabasis* (1.2.9) where Clearchus (the Spartan exile) arrived with 1,000 hoplites, 800 Thracian peltasts (yet another cultural/fighting style association) and 200 Cretan archers. It is unclear if there were other contingents of archers but none are mentioned. After the defeat at Cunaxa in 401 BCE and during the March of the 10,000 both the Cretan archers and Rhodian slingers took on an important role. At *Anabasis* 3.3.6-18 we are told that the Greeks suffered when harassed by Mithridates because the mounted Persian bows could outdistance the Cretan ones and that ‘being light troops’ they had taken position inside the square of the march. Another translation of this phrase at 3.3.7 is that ‘they had no armour’ although it does appear they had shields (see below). Xenophon chose a group of 200 Rhodians who ‘know how to use a sling’ to defend the march. The Rhodians were on the expedition, not as slingers (Xenophon only mentions javelin-men and Cretan archers), but skill in that weapon was considered, for lack of a better term, a national trait. They could outrange the Persian slingers and most of the Persian archers. At 3.4.17 Xenophon expands upon this telling us that the Persians used a bigger bow but that the Cretans were able to pick up the spent Persian arrows and re-use them ‘and practised long-range shooting with a high trajectory.’ The re-use of Persian arrows implies that the Cretan bows cannot have been too dissimilar in size. At 4.2.28, when the Greeks were in difficult terrain, Xenophon tells us that:

‘In this type of country the Cretans were extremely useful. Stratocles, a Cretan himself, was their commander.’

This recalls the training prescribed in Plato’s *Laws* (625D). Given that the unit of 200 Rhodians were extremely useful in keeping the pursuing enemy at bay, there is no need to assume that any more than the 200 Cretan archers we know of were also present and, what is more, that it was this relatively small number that was so effective. Their effectiveness is recalled by Alexander in

Arrian's *Anabasis* (2.7.7-8) although we must be wary that this may have been Arrian's own invention because of his great admiration for Xenophon.

The idea that the Cretan archers wore shields can be seen at *Anabasis* 5.2.29-32 where Xenophon tells us that a certain Mysus took ten Cretan archers on an ambush but that their brass shields kept flashing into sight. This raises the idea of the greater versatility of the Cretan archer, and the possibility that they could operate as light-armed troops as well as just archers. This may also suggest a solution to the idea of Cretan youth training in peltast techniques of shield and archery (Plato *Laws* 834A-D). It is also possible that Cretan archers had some form of specialised light armour. Livy 42.55.10 speaks of *Cretico maxime armatu* 'Cretan arms' although the phrase may simply mean they were armed with the bow. This passage also allows us to see that non-Cretans were equipped and trained in the Cretan fashion (but may still have been known as Cretan archers within the make-up of an army). Livy states that 1,500 Achaeans contributed to the army of Publius Licinius in 171 BCE but that they were mostly equipped with Cretan weaponry (*Cretico maxime armatu*). The idea in Polybius, that the Cretans were cowardly in the face-to-face charge of open battle, perhaps implies that they were sometimes in that position, perhaps because they were equipped with shields and so not 'simply' archers. This may correspond with the flexible training implied in Plato.

At the battle of Nemea in 394, Xenophon tells us that there were 300 Cretan archers on the side of the Spartans (*Hellenica* 4.2.16). The presence of Cretan archers in Spartan armies during this time can be assumed relatively safely to be a constant since at *Hellenica* 4.7.6 Xenophon mentions them plundering Nauplia in 388 rather than being present to shoot down the Boeotian cavalry outside Argos. The appeal of plunder was, of course, to remain a common problem for all employers of mercenary forces. Another Cretan we can assume to have been an archer in the service of Sparta is the individual who warned Agesilaus of the approach of Epaminondas' forces towards an undefended Sparta in 362 (*Hellenica* 7.5.10). Agesilaus had probably had good service from Cretan archers in the East and so continued to use them in mainland Greece. They must have been considered both cost effective and a good investment for their presence seems to have been continuous. Since Clearchus was already using Cretan archers in 401 we can assume Spartan armies had an even longer history of using them although explicit evidence is lacking. It should be noted, however, that Diodorus (15.82.6-83.2) calls these troops 'Cretan runners.' Diodorus' account differs here from the others we have and we should still probably associate these Cretan runners with mercenary Cretan archers in Agesilaus' army. Plato has Clinias describe Cretans as runners

(*Laws* 625D) at the same time as archers. They were certainly diligent and carried out their orders efficiently.

The 500 Cretans sent to Philip by the Polyrrhenians (Polybius 4.55.5-6) are mentioned again at 4.61.2 along with 300 slingers, his Macedonians and the levy of Epirotes. It is clear these Cretan forces are meant to be understood as archers. At 4.67.3 Polybius names the forces taken by Philip to Corinth as consisting of ‘three thousand of his brazen-shield hoplites, two thousand peltasts, three hundred Cretans, and about four hundred of his horse guards.’ Some of these Cretans ‘who had left their ranks and were prowling about in search of plunder’ (4.68.3) betrayed Philip’s presence. This searching for plunder suggests further that they were mercenaries and reinforces that they were archers.

Alexander and Beyond

We also find several references to Cretan archers used by Alexander the Great who seems to have taken advantage of their skill and versatility. The first mention of them in Arrian’s *Anabasis*, however, reinforces the idea that when our sources mention simply ‘archers’ they can imply that specifically Cretan archers are meant. Attacking the Thebans in 335, Alexander brought his forces to aid Perdiccas (Arrian *Anabasis* 1.8.3-5):

He ordered the archers and Agrianians to run out in advance behind the palisade ...

The troops who had broken in with him along with Alexander’s archers hemmed the Thebans into the sunken road ... Eurybotas the Cretan, commander of the archers, fell with about seventy of his men.’

We are originally only told of ‘Alexander’s archers’ but later in the same passage their Cretan commander is named and it would seem logical to assume that they were Cretan archers, or perhaps archers trained in the Cretan manner (and who may still have been considered ‘Cretan’ archers).

Alexander also took 1,000 ‘archers’ and Agrianians with him into Asia (Diodorus 17.17) but it is clear these were Cretans, a sure sign of the quality and value for money such mercenaries provided. At the battle of Issus (*Anabasis* 2.9.3) Arrian tells us that the Cretan archers were posted on the left wing with the Thracians and commanded by Sitalces. Some of these mercenary archers were then transferred to the right wing to affect the outflanking of the Persian line. Alexander clearly used his Cretan archers in combination with other troop types to achieve battlefield aims, a literal use

of combined arms tactics. The archers with some Agrianians sallied forth and dislodged the enemy from the heights. These Thracians/Agrianians are another specialist light-armed unit from Thrace armed with javelins and were clearly paired by Alexander with the Cretan archers. At Gaugamela, Diodorus names the Cretan archers in the formation (17.57.4). Later in 331 BCE (*Anabasis* 3.5.6) Ombrion, a Cretan, was appointed as the commander of the archers. The recording of the names of the (mostly Cretan) commanders of the various Cretan archer contingents in Xenophon and Arrian constitutes a roll of honour for their service. Another such commander is named by Polyaeus (*Strategemata* 4.17). There he records a ruse against Seleucus' generals Achaeus and Andromachus where a Cretan officer, Philetaerus, was sent to negotiate for the body of Antiochus. Antiochus had spread a rumour that he had been killed but when men came to take the surrender of Antiochus' forces, his troops attacked them. This seems the kind of ruse ideal for a commander of light-armed or missile troops so Philetaerus may well have been a commander of the archers.

Polybius has many references to 'Cretans,' especially in the forces of the *Diadochi* and in foreign armies without necessarily calling them Cretan archers although it seems clear from the context that they are, and indeed by naming a Cretan unit he was identifying them as such. What is more, they are often on both sides of opposing combatants. Philip V had 'his own Cretans' (Polybius 5.3.2) who guarded the rear of his march (5.7.11). Philip then learned (5.14.1) that a force, including 500 mercenary Cretans, had been raised against him. In the build-up to the battle of Raphia Ptolemy IV had 2,000 Cretans and 1,000 Neocretans (5.65.7) while Antiochus had 1,500 Cretans and 1,000 Neocretans (5.79.10). Antiochus' commander of the Neocretans was one Zelys of Gortyna, revealing that town's continued association with archery. Diodorus also refers to Cretan archers in the army of Demetrius Poliorcetes (20.85.3) in 305 BCE. We know that there were recruitment officers in Crete and treaties survive for cities to provide troops for Antigonos Dason.

Romans Too?

500 Cretans, in service to Hiero of Syracuse, were sent (along with 1,000 peltasts) to aid Gnaeus Servillius and Gaius Flaminius during the Second Punic War (Polybius 3.75.7-8). Again, it is understood that these Cretans were archers. It is entirely possible that Hiero had more Cretan archers at his disposal. Cretan archers continued to be hired by Roman commanders and their enemies (Livy 43.7.1). Perseus recruited 3,000 Cretans under Syllus of Gnosus (Livy 42.51.7) but this was double what had been sent to Publius Licinius to fight him in 171 BCE. Gaius Gracchus had a contingent of Cretan archers to fight against Fulvius (Plutarch *Gaius Gracchus* 16.3). Strabo records (10.477) that Mithridates V appointed a certain Dorylaeus to recruit mercenaries in Greece,

Thrace and Crete. And Appian (*Civil Wars* 2.49) tells us that Caesar had Cretan archers at Brundisium ready to face Pompey. Caesar himself mentions Cretan archers at *Gallic Wars* 2.7 (along with Numidian archers and Balearic slingers). When Caesar elsewhere mentions archers without any specific origin for them (such as at 2.10) we are safe in assuming that some of them, at least, were those from Crete. Elsewhere Caesar generally mentions legions, cavalry, auxiliaries and light-armed troops in engagements (sometimes even ‘all his forces’) without specifying which units or if there were archers included. He also mentions missiles as being effective in several engagements without specifying if they were javelin, stone or arrow, or a mixture. Again, in most cases we would be safe in assuming that archers (and therefore Cretans) were involved. At the Battle of the Sabis (2.24) for instance, Caesar mentions that the Numidians (these could be the archers mentioned at 2.7 or they may be light-armed troops mentioned at 2.10) routed along with the cavalry and slingers. The Cretans are not mentioned in this context so we might assume they were elsewhere on the field.

But Why Cretans?

This has not been an exhaustive survey of all references to Cretan archers in ancient warfare (indeed, we have only just arrived at Julius Caesar!) but it is clear that, throughout the ancient world, the name ‘Cretan’ was synonymous with quality, cost effective, mercenary archery and vast numbers of young men from the cities of that island (and, more than likely, men from elsewhere who took up ‘Cretan’ identity to form part of a unit or who were trained in the Cretan manner), trained and were hired as mercenary archers to all manner of armies over a vast stretch of time.

Further Reading

J. M. Bigwood ‘Ctesias as historian of the Persian Wars’, *Phoenix* 32 (1978), 19-41.

G. T. Griffith *The Mercenaries of the Hellenistic World* (Cambridge, 1935).